

Haematological and Biochemical Indices of Wistar Rats Fed with Corn Silk-supplemented Diet

Ojo, Folasade Tinuade

Department of Biological Sciences, Tai Solarin University of Education,
Ijagun, Ijebu-Ode, Ogun State, Nigeria

Abstract

Corn silks are being used in traditional medicine for the treatment of various ailments. The haematological and biochemical profiles of Wistar rats fed with corn silk-supplemented diet were investigated. Twenty-five albino rats divided into five groups were used for the study. Group 1 was fed with corn silk (CS) and conventional feed (CF) in ratio 1:2, Group 2 was fed CS and CF in ratio 1:1, Group 3 was fed with CS and CF in ratio 2:1, Group 4 was fed with CF only, Group 5 was fed with CS only. The proximate composition and phytochemical constituents of corn silk were determined while haematological and biochemical indices of animals were measured. The result revealed that corn silk was rich in carbohydrate (60.32%) and crude fiber (19.76%), had abundance of calcium (573.33mg/kg), magnesium (150.00mg/kg), phenol and saponin. The packed cell volume, haemoglobin and red blood cells were found to be higher ($p < 0.05$) in animals fed with 2:1 of CS: CF compared to 1:2 of CS: CF. Glucose level was significantly higher in animals fed with 2:1 of CS: CF (119.45 mg/dl), cholesterol, high density lipoprotein and low density lipoprotein levels were lower ($p < 0.05$) in animals fed with corn silk only. The study concluded that corn silks are good source of energy, rich in crude fiber which can stimulate digestion and aid in immune function. The industrial production and commercialization of corn silk need to be prioritized in order to utilize it as a supplement.

Keywords: Haemoglobin, Cholesterol, Calcium, Carbohydrate, Lipoprotein.

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Corresponding Author: fagbemift@tasued.edu.ng

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Zea mays, widely refer to as corn is among the three leading global cereals that are consumed worldwide (Erenstein *et al.*, 2022). It is significant grain globally after wheat and rice in terms of total production (Erenstein *et al.*, 2022). Zea mays can be grown as single or mixed cropping by small and large-scale farmers. It contains the major calories needed by consumers who cannot afford expensive food items like meat, milk and bread (Adeola *et al.*, 2023).

Corn silks (*Stigmamaydis*) are soft, thread-like and glossy strands that grow on top of the corn cob (Lapcik *et al.*, 2023). They are about 10-20 cm long, light green or yellow

brown in colour with moderate sweet taste (Archana *et al.*, 2016). It is cheap and available immensely during the corn harvest season (Sarepoua *et al.*, 2015), but mostly considered as waste materials since ancient time with little or no knowledge about its importance (Lapcik *et al.*, 2023).

As an herbal remedy, corn silk has been used for centuries in traditional Chinese and Native American medicine. It is employed up till today in various countries such as China, France, Turkey and the United State (Hill, 2023). It is used as remedy for health conditions such as diabetes, hyperlipidemia, cancer, cardiovascular diseases, as well as other chronic and age-related diseases (Mada *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, corn silk

(CS) can be taken in form of tea or as supplement to help address issues related to urinary tract (Karami *et al.*, 2014). With these acclaimed benefits, corn silks are still overlooked by so many people as it is always taken out with the corn husk and discarded as waste. Hence, this study investigates the haematological and biochemical indices of Wistar rats fed with corn silk-supplemented diet.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant material

The fresh and mature corn silk was harvested from farmland in Mamu, Ogun State in July 2023. The corn silk was verified by a taxonomist in the Biological Sciences Department at Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State. The freshly collected corn silk was air dried at room temperature.

2.2 Experimental diet

Growers' mash (Top feed) which is one of the conventional feed given to laboratory animals was supplemented with varying proportion of corn silk and pelletized for the experiment.

2.3 Phytochemical and Mineral Composition

The phytochemical constituents such as flavonoids, saponins, tannins and alkaloids were determined using method described by Njoku *et al.* (2011). Determination of mineral constituents was conducted using method of Rahman and Rosli (2014).

2.4 Proximate composition

Ash content, moisture, carbohydrate, protein and total fibre of corn silk were measured using method outlined by AOAC (2005).

2.5 Source of experimental animals

A total number of 25 male Wistar rats weighing 120-130g that were bred at animal facility of Tai Solarin University of Education were used for the study. The rats were

examined to be free from pathogens and were screened against gastrointestinal parasite. The animals were given time to adjust in the laboratory of Biological Sciences Department, Tai Solarin University of Education for one week in a well-ventilated plastic cage. The animals were provided with the supplemented feed and clean water.

2.6 Ethical consideration

The ethical conditions guidelines for the utilization of laboratory animals were followed as outlined in the guide for Animal Research: Reporting In Vivo Experiments (ARRIVE). The experimental plan was authorized by Department of Biological Sciences Research Ethics Committee Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State.

2.7 Experimental design

Twenty-five albino rats were separated into five groups, and fed with a total of 150g of supplemented diet daily for two weeks.

Group A: was fed with a ratio of 2:1 of corn silk and conventional feed

Group B: was fed with ratio of 1:1 of corn silk and conventional feed

Group C: was fed with a ratio of 1:2 of corn silk and conventional feed

Group D: was fed conventional feed (CF) only

Group E: was fed with corn silk (CS) only

2.8 Collection of blood sample

Blood samples were drawn from the retro-orbital sinus of the albino rats from each group after two weeks of being fed with the supplemented diet. The samples were collected in bottles containing ethylenediamine-tetraacetic acid (EDTA) for haematological assessment using the method outlined by Dacie and Lewis (2001). For Biochemical studies, the blood sample was collected into plain tubes and centrifuged at 1000rpm for 5 min. The serum obtained was collected using Pasteur pipette and placed into sample bottles for

biochemical studies using kits from Randox Laboratories Ltd UK.

2.9 Data Analysis

Data was subjected to Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22 and analyzed using One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Tukey Post hoc test. The results were expressed as mean \pm SE, p-value < 0.05 was considered significant.

3.0 RESULTS

Table 1 presents the proximate composition of corn silk. Dry matter was significantly abundant in corn silk (92.93 %) followed by carbohydrate (60.32%) while crude fat was found to be the least (1.85 %). However, calcium was dominant in corn silk (573.33 mg/kg) followed by magnesium (150.00 mg/kg) while copper was the least abundant (18.12 mg/kg) (Table 2). The phytochemical constituents of corn silk are presented in Table 3. Phenol was abundant in corn silk (46.21 mg/100g) followed by saponin (17.44 mg/100g) and flavonoid was the least abundant (5.23 mg/100g).

Table 4 shows the haematological indices of animals fed with supplemented diet. The packed cell volume (PCV), haemoglobin (Hb) and red blood cells (RBC) were found to be higher ($p < 0.05$) in animals fed with 2:1 of CS: CF when compared with animals fed with 1:2 of CS:CF. The PCV was lower in animals fed with only corn silk. The white blood cells (WBC) were significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) in animals fed with 2:1 CS: CF ($2250 \times 10^3 \mu\text{L}$) when compared with other test groups. The platelet count was higher ($p < 0.05$) in animals fed with corn silk only ($133666.66 \mu\text{L}$) when compared with other groups. Animals fed with corn silk to conventional feed in 1:2 revealed to have higher neutrophils, but lower lymphocytes when compared with other combination ratios ($p < 0.05$). However, eosinophils were recorded to be lower in animals fed with conventional feed only.

Table 1: Proximate Composition of Corn silk

Parameters (%)	Mean \pm S.E	p-value
Crude protein	11.84 \pm 0.03	
Crude fibre	19.76 \pm 0.04	
Crude fat	1.85 \pm 0.00	0.00
Dry matter	92.93 \pm 0.02	
Ash content	6.34 \pm 0.04	
Carbohydrate	60.32 \pm 0.15	

Values are presented as means \pm standard error and are considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$. N=3 per parameter

Table 2: Mineral composition of Corn silk

Parameters (mg/kg)	Mean \pm S.E	p-value
Calcium	573.33 \pm 0.00	
Magnesium	150.00 \pm 0.00	
Zinc	29.50 \pm 0.15	0.00
Copper	18.12 \pm 0.05	
Phosphorus	33.21 \pm 0.00	
Iron	85.90 \pm 1.10	

Values are presented as means \pm standard error and are considered significant at $p \leq 0.05$. N=3 per parameter.

Table 3: Phytochemical constituents of corn silk

Parameters (mg/100g)	Mean \pm S.E	p-value
Phenols	46.21 \pm 0.12	
Flavonoid	5.23 \pm 0.03	
Saponin	17.44 \pm 0.08	0.00
Tannin	15.81 \pm 0.01	
Alkaloid	7.23 \pm 0.02	

Values are expressed as means \pm standard error and are deemed significant at $p \leq 0.05$. N=3 per parameter.

Table 4: Hematological indices of animals fed with corn silk and conventional feed

Groups	PCV (%)	Hb (g/dL)	RBC ($\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$)	WBC ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	PLATELET (μL)	LYM (%)	NEUT (%)	MONO (%)	EOSI (%)
CS:CF 1:2	40.33 \pm 0.33 ^a	13.03 \pm 0.03 ^a	6.59 \pm 0.00 ^a	2900.00 \pm 250.00 ^b	92666.66 \pm 3333.33 ^a	68.33 \pm 3.33 ^a	28.00 \pm 1.00 ^b	1.33 \pm 0.33 ^a	3.00 \pm 0.00 ^{bc}
CS:CF 1:1	44.00 \pm 0.00 ^b	14.63 \pm 0.07 ^b	7.38 \pm 0.01 ^b	3050.00 \pm 50.00 ^b	87000.00 \pm 3000.00 ^a	73.33 \pm 0.33 ^b	22.00 \pm 1.00 ^a	1.67 \pm 0.67 ^a	3.00 \pm 0.00 ^{bc}
CS:CF 2:1	44.67 \pm 1.33 ^b	14.67 \pm 0.33 ^b	7.55 \pm 2.26 ^b	2250 \pm 288.67 ^a	89333.33 \pm 24666.66 ^a	74.33 \pm 0.67 ^b	20.00 \pm 1.00 ^a	2.00 \pm 0.00 ^a	3.67 \pm 0.33 ^c
CF only	45.67 \pm 0.33 ^b	15.17 \pm 0.13 ^b	7.52 \pm 0.01 ^b	2850.00 \pm 50.00 ^b	88333.33 \pm 6333.33 ^a	75.33 \pm 0.67 ^b	20.67 \pm 0.67 ^{ab}	2.33 \pm 0.33 ^a	1.67 \pm 0.33 ^a
CS only	40.67 \pm 1.67 ^a	12.87 \pm 0.67 ^a	6.69 \pm 0.38 ^a	2900.00 \pm 100.00 ^b	133666.66 \pm 5333.33 ^b	73.33 \pm 1.76 ^b	22.33 \pm 1.76 ^a	1.67 \pm 0.67 ^a	2.33 \pm 0.33 ^{ab}

Values are presented as means \pm standard error, for n= 5 rats /group. Columns containing values with the same superscript are not significantly different (p>0.05).PCV- Packed cell volume Hb- Haemoglobin RBC- Red blood cell WBC- White blood cell LYM- Lymphocytes NEUT- Neutrophils MONO-Monocytes EOSI- Eosinophil.

Table 5 shows the biochemical parameters of animals fed with corn silk supplemented diet. Glucose level was significantly higher in animals fed with 2:1 of corn silk to conventional feed (119.45 mg/dl) followed by animals fed with ratio 1: 2 (corn silk to conventional feed). Cholesterol was found to be lower in animals fed with 2:1 of the supplemented feed when compared with other supplemented feed ratios. However, cholesterol, High density

lipoprotein (HDL) and Low density lipoprotein (LDL) levels were lower (p<0.05) in animals fed with corn silk only when compared with test animals. The high density lipoprotein was higher in animals fed with corn silk and conventional feed in ratio 2:1. Total protein was highest in animals fed with corn silk to conventional feed (2:1) (Table 5).

Table 5: Biochemical indices of animals fed with corn silk and conventional feed

Groups	GLU (mg/dL)	CHOL (mg/dL)	TG (mg/dL)	HDL (mg/dL)	LDL (mg/dL)	TP (g/dL)	ALB (g/dL)
CS:CF 1:2	94.83 \pm 8.30 ^{ab}	112.84 \pm 5.39 ^c	73.08 \pm 0.76 ^a	53.01 \pm 4.88 ^a	45.20 \pm 0.35 ^b	4.45 \pm 0.29 ^{ab}	3.41 \pm 0.09 ^a
CS:CF 1:1	93.84 \pm 0.03 ^{ab}	152.47 \pm 4.45 ^d	78.75 \pm 60 ^a	47.36 \pm 4.57 ^a	89.35 \pm 8.30 ^c	4.43 \pm 0.38 ^{ab}	3.25 \pm 0.09 ^a
CS:CF 2:1	119.45 \pm 14.01 ^b	100.45 \pm 1.62 ^b	67.53 \pm 4.02 ^a	65.73 \pm 1.08 ^b	21.21 \pm 1.90 ^a	4.93 \pm 0.02 ^b	3.35 \pm 0.01 ^a
CF only	78.91 \pm 0.14 ^a	112.64 \pm 1.66 ^c	74.87 \pm 7.18 ^a	73.48 \pm 0.23 ^b	24.18 \pm 0.26 ^a	4.43 \pm 0.28 ^{ab}	3.39 \pm 0.15 ^a
CS only	92.38 \pm 11.16 ^{ab}	78.97 \pm 4.10 ^a	66.67 \pm 2.94 ^a	47.44 \pm 1.39 ^a	18.20 \pm 4.91 ^a	3.73 \pm 0.17 ^a	3.10 \pm 0.07 ^a

Values are presented as means \pm standard error, for n= 5 rats/group. Columns containing values with the same superscript are not significantly different (p>0.05) GLU- glucose CHOL- Cholesterol TG-Triglyceride TP- Total protein ALB- Albumin.

4.0 DISCUSSION

Corn silk which is often regarded as waste product of corn has been utilised in traditional medicines for the treatment of a variety of ailments. The proximate composition of a plant is important in the determination of bioactive substances in plants. This study revealed that corn silk is rich in carbohydrate. This suggests that is a good source of glucose which can provide energy for the body. This agrees with the findings of Olaniyan and Fadare (2014) who observed that corn silk is high in carbohydrates, vitamins and proteins. The low crude fat recorded in this study indicates that corn silk could help in weight management and reduce the chance of heart disease. However, the crude fat content in this study surpassed the earlier report of 0.29 % (Wang *et al.*, 2011). The study also revealed that protein is one of the bioactive substances in corn silk. However, the crude protein of corn silk recorded in this study exceeds the value of 8.95% reported by Rahman and Wan Rosli (2014) in mature corn silk. The protein content of corn silkin this study is higher than mango peels (7.03-8.6% %) (Wongkaew *et al.*, 2021), *Garcinia kola* (3.19%), (Omeh *et al.*, 2014) and vegetable like pumpkin (6.5%) (Fai *et al.*, 2013).

To produce grains with higher yield, it is important to determine the dry matter content. The high dry matter recorded in corn silk in this study indicates its high nutritional content. The abundance of mineral elements in a plant is reflected in its ash content (Iniaghe *et al.*, 2009). The ash content of corn silk (6.34%) in this study is higher than earlier reports of 5.4% (Sumarli *et al.*, 2019) and 5.51% (Rahman and Wan Rosli, 2014). Environmental factors, age of plant at harvest, diurnal and seasonal changes, geographic location and method could be attributed for the variation in composition (Mgbeje *et al.*, 2019).

Minerals have various important functions in living organisms and act as co-factors in specific biochemical processes including

those related to antioxidant enzymes. High level of calcium and magnesium recorded in this study agrees with the findings of Rahman and Rosli (2014) where similar high level of calcium was reported in mature silk. Calcium plays a role in contraction of muscle, nerve signaling, cell movement and division by acting as signal transmitter between the exterior and interior of the cell while magnesium is important in muscle function, blood pressure and making of protein (Gröber *et al.*, 2015; Mgbeje *et al.*, 2019).

Phytochemicals are seen as potentially valuable compounds for creating environmentally friendly products because they break down easily and have fewer negative effects than synthetic drugs (Shahidi and Zhong, 2010). The presence of flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids, and phenol in corn silk with their varied quantities suggest that corn silk consist some beneficial bioactive compounds that may have played a role in their well-known medicinal benefits. The abundance of phenol and saponin in corn silk indicates that it could help to protect cells from damage caused by free radical and assist to remove fatty compounds from the body (Ene-Obong *et al.*, 2016). This agrees with Singh *et al.* (2022) who reported high level of phenol in corn silk.

Assessment of blood is useful in diagnosis of diseases and pathological conditions. The decrease in packed cell volume, haemoglobin and red blood cells of animals fed with corn silk only and combination of CS and CF in 1:2 when compared with other groups suggest inhibition of erythropoietin production from the stem cells of the animals (Nwankpa and Ezinne, 2022). However, the increase in WBC of animal fed with CS: CF in ratios 1:2, 1:1and CS only suggest the presence of some phytochemicals which boost the immune system while the decrease in WBC at 2:1 of CS and CF could be attributed to immune system of rats reacting to foreign compounds (Saheed *et al.*, 2015).The increase in lymphocytes of some animals that were fed with corn silk

could be a plausible explanation for its activity on the effectors cells of the immune system. The elevated level of platelets in animals fed with corn silk only indicates that it stimulates the production of new platelets, helps to heal small vascular injuries and effectively treat thrombocytopenia in animals (Geddis, 2013).

Biochemical parameters serve as valuable indicators for assessing the health of animals and humans. The increase in glucose level of animals fed with 2:1 of corn silk and conventional feed might be due to high carbohydrate content found in corn silk. The proximate analysis of corn silk in this study revealed it is abundant in carbohydrate. The reduction in cholesterol, HDL and LDL levels of animals fed with corn silk only indicates that corn silk could enhance metabolism of lipids in the body. This could be as result of bioactive substances such as flavonoids, saponin which have potential to lower lipid in the body. This agrees with the findings of Nwankpa and Ezinne (2022) that corn silk has hypolipidaemic effect.

5.0 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the study showed that corn silk contains useful bioactive substances which is responsible for its usage in traditional medicine. Furthermore, corn silk is rich in carbohydrate which is good source energy and can also boost immune system by production of white blood cells. Corn silk has ability to lower blood cholesterol and remove fatty compounds from the body.

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8.0 CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The author expressed no conflict of interests.

9.0 AUTHOR'S CONTRIBUTIONS

OFT conceptualized this research, analysed the data and developed the manuscript.

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